

AI-PRISM

D8.2– AI-PRISM Dissemination and Communication Report (I)

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AUS	MTU AUSTRALO ALPHA LAB
CEA	Comité Español de Automática
CRAN	Cranfield University
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
ETRI	Electronics And Telecommunications Research Institute
EU	European Union
ERF	European Robotics Forum
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HPS	Hybrid Production Systems
HRC	Human-Robot Collaboration
ITI	Instituto Tecnológico De Informatica
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NTTD ES	NTT DATA SPAIN, SL
NTTD RO	NTT DATA ROMANIA SA
PIAP	SIEC BADAWCZA LUKASIEWICZ - Przemyslowy Instytut Automatyki I Pomiarow
ROB	ROBOTNIK AUTOMATION SL
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TAU	Tampere University
TDIH	Asociatia Transilvania IT
UPV	Universitat Politecnica De Valencia
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Abstract

Communication and Dissemination are vital elements of any successful Horizon Europe funded project. Building on the **AI-PRISM's** Impact Master Plan, which defined the goals, priorities and any potential implementation mechanisms to achieve all desirable outcomes, the present document presents an overview of the AI-PRISM's Communication, Dissemination and International Cooperation activities implemented and the main results during the **first 18 months** of life of the project.

Executive summary

AI-PRISM functions in a decentralized fashion, overseeing a varied group of organizations, projects, and key stakeholders. To boost its influence, the initiative needs a flexible growth catalyst that cultivates fresh synergies over the course of the project.

For this purpose, **AI-PRISM** adopted an Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework, a methodology being implemented to continuously develop and strengthen relationships with key stakeholder groups.

AI-PRISM is implementing a targeted but wide communication approach, focused on reaching target groups and stakeholders effectively, and based on:

- Highlighting key aspects and benefits of the AI-PRISM project
- Creation of clear and easily understandable visual materials
- Dissemination of relevant information through AI-PRISM communication channels
- Utilizing project deliverables, partner interviews, pilot case studies, and industry reports to engage users

Through the dissemination actions being implemented, **AI-PRISM** is aiming at sharing its results with diverse stakeholders, and making results accessible to the broader community.

Hence, the dissemination activities are focused on raising awareness, fostering understanding, and generating actionable outcomes among the target audience, in order to boost the adoption of the project outcomes and research insights.

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with **human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable, and high-quality European manufacturing industry.**

To do so, we will develop an **integrated and scalable environment** with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. **A human-robot cooperative environment** powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability, and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances, and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.**

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, **AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes**, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the three years of duration of the project, **25 partners** from **12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

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Introduction

The current document (8.2 – AI-PRISM Dissemination and Communication Report (I)) is part of AI-PRISM WP8 – Outreach, Exploitation and Collaboration, specifically focusing on Tasks T8.1 – Stakeholder Collaboration Framework, T8.2 – Dissemination and Communication, and T8.5 – International Cooperation.

This report offers a **comprehensive overview of all the significant communication, dissemination, and international cooperation activities** conducted throughout the project's duration up to this point. It also presents quantitative data on the performance of our digital platforms, participation in both physical and online events, as well as scientific and awareness publications.

The overall Communication, Dissemination, and International Cooperation strategy was initially outlined in deliverable D8.1 – AI-PRISM Impact Master Plan. Therefore, this document builds upon the content of D8.1 to provide a clear update in the form of the project's interim report at M18.

In terms of structure, D8.2 consists of three interlinked areas. While section 1 and 5 are the introductory and conclusive sections of the document, the other three present and discuss the **implementation of tasks 8.1, 8.2, and 8.5 up to M18**. More specifically, sections 2 to 4 discuss the following subjects:

- **Section 2** provides a clear overview of the activities performed under Task 8.1 AI-PRISM's Engagement Framework, the methodology of identifying and engaging with high-interest stakeholders (groups or individuals).
- **Section 3** explains all actions involved in Task 8.2 Communication & Dissemination to increase the outreach of the project.
- **Section 4** explains the activities of Task 8.5 International cooperation.

AI-PRISM's Engagement Framework – Status M18

As a Horizon Europe action, **AI-PRISM** is an initiative that is decentralised by nature, but with the need for managing an ecosystem of organisations, initiatives and players with a given position of influence on the project's performance - the stakeholders.

The initiative requires a responsive growth factor capable of prospecting and creating brand new synergies over the project's lifetime, facilitating a greater advantage and extending its range of action. For that, **AI-PRISM** is implementing an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework** - a methodology designed to continuously develop and strengthen work streams with key stakeholder groups. This methodology has three main phases:

- Scouting: where it identifies and assesses target groups, creating a Stakeholders Map.
- Interacting: when it engages with these groups to align activities with project strategies.
- Learning: when insights are gathered for future iterations.

Stakeholders include the Manufacturing Industry, Digital Tech Providers, Social Innovation Sector, and Advocate Ecosystem.

The Stakeholders Map categorizes stakeholders based on their influence and interest, facilitating tailored engagement strategies introduced in the Grant Agreement.

Mechanism's Phases

This mechanism follows an **iterative approach** based on **Sprints**; time-boxes of **six months** with three **phases** where the main goal is to increase and reinforce such engagement incrementally.

PHASE 1: Scouting

During this phase, the **Target Groups** -and specific candidates- were identified, resulting in an initial '**Stakeholders Map**'.

The initial Stakeholders Map categorizes stakeholders based on their influence and interest, facilitating tailored engagement strategies introduced in the Grant Agreement, and was included in M8 (D.8.1).

This European ecosystem map was drafted by the partners by mapping and narrowing down any possible target groups which could be interested in AI-PRISMs activities and could be engaged throughout the whole duration of the projects. It is being used as a basis for the initial contacts and further sprints.

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Figure 1 AI-PRISM's Stakeholder Map

In following Sprints further scouting continued to develop and refine the Agile Marketing Lab Framework. This map is continuously updated with the new actors found, either through the project activities or through intentional search actions.

PHASE 2: Interacting

This stage implies the interaction as such with the identified target groups, supporting the activities outlined in the **Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies**.

After a first sprint of Stakeholders' scouting, more than 50 relevant actors were detected, which lead to the interaction with over 30 entities.

AI-PRISM partners have established links with several initiatives, such as the other three **sister projects** ([COGNIMAN](#), [FLUENTLY](#) and [CONVERGING](#)), funded by the same call, as well as with other **Horizon Europe projects** such as [ULTIMATE](#), [FELICE](#), [ODIN](#), [JARVIS](#), [AGILE HAND](#), [FEROX](#), [RESPECT](#), [MERGING](#) and ZER0P .

European Networks and platforms, such as [EFFRA](#) (European Factories of the Future Research Association), [CEA](#) (Comité Español de Automática) or EIT manufacturing.

The **Hybrid Production Systems (HPS) cluster** consists of over 40 EU-funded projects (FP7, H2020, Horizon Europe) dealing with hybrid production and promoting knowledge and experience sharing, aiming to define the roadmap for Hybrid Production Systems.

As an example of this continued close collaboration with other initiatives to leverage their expertise and resources for mutual benefit, is the **organization of joint activities** (such as workshops during the European Robotics Forum 2023 and 2024 editions) and **cross-dissemination** with several of the AI-PRISM sister projects.

PHASE 3: Learning

The final objective is to achieve a high involvement of these actors, as well as new ones, in AI-PRISM activities in order to create a collaborative ecosystem. The progress made during these months has set a strong foundation for the remainder of the project. Further research of the ecosystem and specific customized outreach campaigns will be implemented per target stakeholder, to increase engagement efforts with EU initiatives, industrial associations, think tanks, and other relevant actors.

We plan to deploy the refined Agile Marketing Lab Framework to further interact with target groups, identifying new actors, and adapt to changing project dynamics.

Communication & Dissemination

A flexible communication and dissemination set of actions and tools are crucial to achieve maximum project impact. As of M18, these actions focused on two main aspects:

- Make the results open and available for the stakeholders to facilitate their usage (dissemination activities)
- Promote and increase the visibility of the project activities, achievements, team, etc. (communication activities)

In the following chapter, a description of the central dissemination and communication activities carried out by the project, up to M18, is presented, focusing on:

- The online channels used
- The promotional material created
- The publications
- The events/workshops participated/organised
- The contents and awareness publications generated
- The campaigns launched

Communication Actions

AI-PRISM communication plan focuses on creating awareness and interest among target groups and stakeholders through a funnelled approach, utilizing visual materials and tailored content. Hence, the objectives include increasing awareness, communicating technical results, delivering top-level messages, and highlighting AI-PRISM's value to diverse audiences.

The communication activities are divided into **three phases**: Plan and revisit, Early bird Communication, and Targeted Communication, each with specific goals and timing.

Various **communication tools**, including websites, social media, articles, and events, are being utilized to ensure effective engagement throughout the project's lifespan.

Phases & Timing

Communication activities will be implemented in three different phases, which are closely related to dissemination as well. The common goal is to create a “buzz” around the project, and to mobilise stakeholders who will interact and provide input to other project activities as well.

PHASE 1: Plan and revisit

The first communication phase started in M1, and the communication activities focused more on drafting any necessary communication tools and strategies to be implemented and used throughout the whole project. More specific, on defining the communication strategy reported in D8.1 - AI-PRISM

Impact Master Plan, including setting up the main communication tools and channels early in the project: [Website](#), [X](#), [LinkedIn](#), [YouTube](#).

Initial communication activities, such as producing launch press releases (in English and Korean), took place during this phase, and are described in the following pages.

PHASE 2: Early bird Communication

The second phase started in M3, with early bird communication activities aiming to communicate both to a wider public and to specific communities, the existence of the project and its main actions.

The focus, during this phase, was put on the online channels and measures, with a wider reach.

In parallel, the AI-PRISM team has implemented several online campaigns throughout social media, presenting the project team and its main aspects activities.

This phase will last for the whole duration of the project as it mainly focuses on communicating the generic aspect of the project to a wide stakeholder base.

PHASE 3: Targeted Communication

The third communication phase started around M8 as it requires the project to be in a more mature stage.

During this phase, targeted communication activities have taken place such as producing and communicating articles, blogs or posts specifically for certain project outcomes and benefits (advances on the pilots and demonstrators, scientific production), hosting and/or participating in physical and online events (such as the European Robotics Forum, the Valencia Digital Summit or the European Big Data Value Forum) for the communication of AI-PRISM's innovations, production of targeted communication material (i.e. videos and creativities) for the community, etc.

This phase runs in parallel with phase 2 as it focuses on targeted communication actions for specific audiences and not on actions for the whole community.

Communication Tools & Material

A set of communication tools will be developed to allow the project to reach the right audiences. All these tools will be produced throughout the whole lifetime of the project and customised if and when needed. Hereunder is a summary of the communication tools developed up to the moment of writing this Deliverable:

Online and Digital Tools

Project website

The AI-PRISM's website, <https://aiprism.eu/> showcases the project's mission, vision and values as well as its main innovations, information about the 5 demonstrators, the opportunities it offers, and

important news and scientific publications. It has been designed following the branding elements set up at the beginning of the project.

All relevant content about the developments of AI-PRISM is published in the News section, with more than 65 pieces at this moment (an average of weekly updates) divided into:

- AI-PRISM stories (interviews and specific campaigns)
- Events
- Newsletters
- Publications (both scientific and awareness ones)
- Public Deliverables

All other sections of the website are updated and adapted as required by the project implementation (change of logos, announcement banners, etc.).

Regarding the most important **metrics since the website's launch** in October 2022 and until the end of February 2024 (17 months), which are taken from Google Analytics: the website has had 909 users, 1.800 sessions started, and **4.400 accumulated views** (251 average monthly views).

A further metrics' analysis regarding the **website sessions by channel**, shows that, for new users, the channel is primarily organic (accessing the link directly with the website address), followed by those coming from social media.

Figure 2 AI-PRISM's website - new users by First user primary channel group (Default Channel Group)

Figure 3 AI-PRISM's website - new users by First user primary channel group (Default Channel Group) over time

As for the **website views** considering the “event” shows a high user engagement, as it can be seen in the graphics under these lines.

Figure 4 AI-PRISM's website – event count by Event name

Figure 5 AI-PRISM's website – event count by Event name over time

The top three **countries** from which most users have visited the website are Ireland, France and Spain.

Figure 6 AI-PRISM's website – users per country

The **pages with the most views** are the home (AI-PRISM - AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing) followed by the News section, as showed in the figure hereunder.

Page title and screen class	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Event count
	4,390 100% of total	795 100% of total	5.52 Avg 0%	1m 37s Avg 0%	12,154 100% of total
1 AI-PRISM – AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing	1,125	348	3.23	37s	3,450
2 News – AI-PRISM	544	91	5.98	1m 30s	1,330
3 Team – AI-PRISM	365	178	2.05	1m 00s	953
4 Project – AI-PRISM	231	143	1.62	51s	580
5 Demonstrators – AI-PRISM	135	83	1.63	44s	360

Figure 7 AI-PRISM's website – pages with more views

Social Media

AI-PRISM has maintained an active presence on all its social media channels: X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn and YouTube, since it started, where it promotes its progress, activities, results and opportunities, and effectively engages its stakeholders. This active presence has allowed AI-PRISM to:

- Accumulate an aggregate audience of **more than 1.450 followers**,
- Reach close to **150,000 post impressions** (monthly average of 8.945) between the three platforms.

Divided per channel, the numbers are distributed as follows, with X in the lead of followers and LinkedIn in post impressions.

- [LinkedIn](#), with 479 followers, 99,724 post impressions, 2,411 page views.
- [X](#), with 972 followers and 49,268 post impressions.
- [YouTube](#) serves as the project's video repository, achieving the following results: 27 videos and short animations uploaded, with close to 700 views.

Different **Marketing Campaigns** have and are currently being implemented, taking advantage of the different stages and results of the project, as well as other current topics happening in the ecosystem.

Some examples of these campaigns are:

- Meet the Team:
 - Meeting Use Case Partners
 - Meeting Industrial Partners
 - Meeting Technology providers and research
 - Meeting Research Partners
- European Year of Skills 2023

- International Day of Education 2023
- International Day of SMEs 2023
- Women in Tech and Science behind AI-PRISM
- Women in Social Sciences behind AI-PRISM
- Women's Day 2024
- Participation of AI-PRISM events where the project will have a relevant role, such as the European Robotics Forum 2023 and 2024, launched in collaboration with sister projects, and containing specific campaigns such as the Workshop Speakers' Campaign or the Call for Papers Campaign.
- Joint campaigns with the Korean partners
- Commemoration of AI-PRISM first anniversary.

These campaigns can include actions such as interviews, the creation of videos and creativities, the collaboration with other initiatives and projects (which entails the coordination of the campaign – joint branding and dissemination toolkit, timing and roadmap of actions, creation of key messages, cross-dissemination activities in social media, gathering of materials in situ, etc.).

Other topics addressed in the AI-PRISM social channels and hashtags used are the following:

- Project updates, facts, objectives or highlights
- #AIPRISMSmartJourney
- #AIPRISM25
- #AIPRISMInnovations
- Relevant industry news, events, opportunities and resources

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AI-PRISM
462 followers
1mo • Edited •

AI-PRISM Project Meeting Wraps Up with Innovation Galore!

As the curtains close on the final substantive sessions of our 2nd AI-PRISM Project Meeting, we're thrilled to share the groundbreaking strides we've made!

Open Experimentation Framework:
Focus on Readiness Level: Our session zeroed in on the Open Experimentation Framework, a pivotal element not included in the first release. While there's no tangible demo yet, we delved deep into the relevant aspects, aligning on readiness levels for the TRM.

Human Behavior Modeling and Analytics Showcase:
Beyond Technical Components: Shifting gears, we explored Human Behavior Modeling and Analytics. Not just technical components, but a glimpse into the very fabric of human interaction. Cranfield University and ETRI showcased experimentation facilities and real experiments, bridging the gap between tech and human behavior.

UPV/EHU Comau lukasiewicz – PIAP NTT DATA Business Solutions Spain
Fondazione Bruno Kessler - FBK KU Leuven Tampere University PROFACOR
IKERLAN KEBA Group Robotnik Automation AUSTRALO Andreu World Silverline
Appliances VIGO Photonics ATHENIAN BREWERY S.A. / ΑΘΗΝΑΙΚΗ ΖΥΘΟΠΟΙΑ
A.E. Cranfield University TEKNOPAR

Perin Ünal, PhD and 44 others
9 reposts

Reactions
+37

AI-PRISM
462 followers
1yr •

If you are interested in collaborative #robotics in #manufacturing scenarios, our workshop at the #DMIS2023 in Valencia es is your must-to-be event!

Today, we unveil more details about the workshop that our Project Coordinator, NTT DATA Europe & Latam, will chair. At the event, representatives from #AIPRISM25 KEBA Group, Tampere University, and Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) will share the floor with Grupo Aldakin and APICUS

Register for FREE <https://bit.ly/3UaGvWp>

#DigitalTranformation #DigitalDecade #HorizonEU #SmartManufacturing

Francisco Fralle, PhD and 13 others
1 repost

Reactions
+6

Figure 8 AI-PRISM's example of social media posts

Newsletters

The AI-PRISM newsletters are produced twice a year and distributed through email using the Brevoo software as well as LinkedIn with 28 and 186 subscribers, respectively, 214 in total.

[The first project newsletter](#), launched in April 2023 contained all the steps of the project during the first 8 months of the project duration, including information such as the introduction to the team, a summary of the technical advancements, events attended, social media campaigns, deliverables, etc.

**WELCOME TO THE
AI-PRISM SMART JOURNEY!
NEWSLETTER #1**

Let's go !

Dear { { contact.FIRSTNAME } } ,

The #AIPRISM25 team gives you a warm welcome to this newsletter #1. Almost eight months ago, we started our project, and since then, many news, events and technical advancements have happened.

As part of the AI-PRISM Smart Journey, you have access to this compilation of activities that are significantly AI-powering, human-centred robot interactions for smart manufacturing.

[Learn more about AI-PRISM!](#)

MEETING OUR PROJECT COORDINATOR

Ana Gonzalez Segura (NTT Data Spain) is our Project Coordinator. She is at the frontline of AI-PRISM, ensuring that all 25 organisations participate, innovate, collaborate, and accomplish a common objective: turning the manufacturing industry and its SMEs into smart through digitalisation.

[Meet her!](#)

INTRODUCING OUR TECHNICAL MANAGER

Francisco Fraile (Polytechnical University of Valencia) is our Technical Manager. He is leading the Technical board of the project, making certain that everyone

based on their expertise.

The #AIPRISM25 is a strong and interdisciplinary team comprising the Smart manufacturing value chain and specifically strategic domains:

- ✓ Collaboration environment
- ✓ Robot perception & cognition
- ✓ Robot programming & Human factors.

Throughout these months, every team member has been working on tasks involving our demonstrators and the project's architecture.

DELIVERABLES

TECHNOLOGY BENCHMARKING & PROJECT VISION

The deliverable presents technologies and the first standards that laid the foundations for developing our project.

[Read more](#)

TASK ANALYSIS FOR BENCHMARKING & DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

The methodology, results, conclusions and future work in the human factors and psychological aspects involved in each use case are part of the content of this deliverable.

[Read more](#)

USE CASE SCENARIOS & REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

The document reports the efforts done in the scope of tasks of the AI-PRISM project towards the definition of the use cases and the requirement analysis specifications.

[Read more](#)

DEMONSTRATORS

We will test our innovations in different manufacturing sectors (furniture, electronics, built-in home appliances, beverages and discrete manufacturing) based in Spain, Poland, Greece, Turkey and Austria.

In these months, the methodology established in the proposal has been followed by our industrial partners, researchers and tech providers. It consisted of:

- ✓ Detailed descriptions of the demonstrators
- ✓ Online workshops
- ✓ Physical visits to start the data collection.

By the 8th month, we had already finished the detailed descriptions of our demonstrators, executed the four online workshops and visited all our use cases.

Figure 9 Extract of AI-PRISM Newsletter 1

The second Newsletter, launched in October 2023, contained all the milestones and technical advancements reached during the first year of the project, the different campaigns implemented, events attended, as well as a video showcasing the project main achievements.

The third number will be published in April 2024, with the latest developments of the project and collaboration opportunities, such as the 2nd General Assembly held in Turin in January 2024, or the attendance to the European Robotics Forum in March 2024.

In addition to the official AI-PRISM newsletter, targeted to an external audience, an **internal newsletter** has been created, in order to keep all partners (and their whole teams) up to date on the ongoing and upcoming activities, avoiding any loss of information, as well as being a way of gathering information for further dissemination actions and the next external newsletter editions. Two internal newsletters have been produced, with the idea of making them twice a year, and timed two months before the release of the external version.

Upcoming events

Good news! Our proposal to organise another workshop at **I-ESA 2024 Flounda, Crete island, Greece (10.04.2024)**: "Enhancing Enterprise Interoperability through Human-Centred Collaborative is accepted!

AI-PRISM is also invited to participate in the ULTIMATE_project's workshop **"Workshop on Ethics, Hybrid AI, Safety & Trustworthiness for robotics and XAI"** on the 2nd February.
Any other events you are planning to attend?

KEEP US POSTED HERE or contact raquel@australo.org and agnieszka@australo.org from Australo to communicate about your participation.

Keep us posted

Check out which Deliverables are next!

Check out which Deliverables are next!

It's easy to check in the [Deliverable Roadmap!](#)

Don't forget about the [guidelines for the review and submission.](#)

What are you up to?

Kind reminder for all Consortium Partners!

COMPLETE THE D&C ACTIVITY LOG BY JANUARY 19TH!

We need your latest information to prepare subsequent dissemination actions, as well as for reporting and follow-up of all Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

D&C Activity Log

Figure 10 Extract of AI-PRISM Internal Newsletter 1

AI-PRISM partners have also included information about the project in their own communication channels, from their social media to their websites (for example [ROB](#), [FBK](#) or [ITI](#)). They have also created entries in their blogs or, for the purpose of this section, in their newsletters.

Other

Press Releases

Intended for press distribution as well as accompanying potential email campaigns, **2 Press Releases** have been produced, announcing the launch and objectives of **AI-PRISM**, **one of them in [English](#) and another in [Korean](#)**, for the partners to communicate the project to their network of customers, members and collaborators. Other Press Releases have been produced for specific milestones of the project, such as the participation in the ERF 2023.

Publish online articles to various international platforms (i.e. [EFFRA](#), [CEA](#)) and on national/local portals, to leverage the **AI-PRISM's** scope and results.

Slide Decks and Templates

With the objective of creating a cohesive and recognizable image of the project, an AI-PRISM Identity kit was produced at the beginning of the project, including:

- Official AI-PRISM logo
- The Branding elements
- Project templates for Deliverables and meeting minutes
- Background images
- AI- PRISM Slide Decks (one generic for the project presentation, updated as needed). Other versions have been produced for specific events if required by the partners.

Printed & Digital Promotional Material

Printed Materials

Regarding ready to print materials, a set of promotional materials has been created and put at the disposal of the partners, for them to distribute at the events, conferences, workshops, etc attended. The communications team updates these materials according to the needs of the project.

The initial [set of promotional materials](#) contains:

- AI-PRISM Flyer
- AI-PRISM Postcard
- AI-PRISM Trifold
- AI-PRISM Roll-up, to display during conferences and events

These materials are produced both in web/online and ready to print versions.

Figure 11 AI-PRISM's Trifold.

On top of the initial set, further materials have been designed, either when new needs have been detected or as requested by the partners, such as:

- **Business cards** to distribute at meetings and events. A digital version has also been created with a QR code that leading to the project website.
- **Posters** for the presentation of papers.

Figure 12 AI-PRISM's Digital Business Card

Figure 13 AI-PRISM's template for the presentation of papers at the Insight Session of the ERF 2024

Multimedia material

Utilising multimedia materials, especially videos, is a captivating and self-explanatory approach to introduce the project to a wide audience through popular video platforms. AI-PRISM has established a dedicated [YouTube channel](#) to upload and disseminate the **26 videos** produced up to this moment, which are about to reach **700 views**.

These edited videos generated by the project have been created with footage gathered by the consortium face-to-face and online meetings and events or at their premises, pertain to the following topics:

The **project's main promotional video**, included on the website and YouTube channel, updated with the project's developments at year 1.

9 videos presenting the team:

- #AIPRISM25: Meeting Project Coordinator 1.0 and Meeting the Technical Manager
- #AIPRISM25: Technology providers
- #AIPRISM25: Technology integrators
- #AIPRISM25: Technology developers

#AIPRISM25 : Meeting Project Coordinator 1.0

#AIPRISM25 : Meeting Project Coordinator 2.0

#AIPRISM25 : Meeting Project Coordinator 3.0

#AIPRISM25 : Meeting Technical Manager 1.0

#AIPRISM25 : Meeting Technical Manager 2.0

#AIPRISM25 : Meeting Technical Manager 3.0

#AIPRISM25 : Technology providers - A&G Republic of Korea

#AIPRISM25 : Technology integrators - Teknopar Industrial Automation

#AIPRISM25 : Technology developers - Ikerlan S. COOP

Figure 14 AI-PRISM's team presentation videos.

2 videos presenting Use-cases:

- #AIPRISM25: Use case – Silverline
- #AIPRISM25: Use case – Athenian Brewery

5 videos presenting the #AIPRISMInnovations:

- #AIPRISMInnovations: Collaborative Robotics in Smart Manufacturing
- #AIPRISMInnovations: Robot Programming by Demonstration
- #AIPRISMInnovations: AI Tools to Enhance Perception, Reasoning & Control
- #AIPRISMInnovations: Social Sciences & Humanities Applied to Collaborative Robotics
- #AIPRISMInnovations: AI-PRISM Real-Time Platform

9 videos presenting other topics, such as:

- #AIPRISMSmartJourney (3 videos)
- #SmartManufacturing (2 videos)
- Transparency

- Ethics and AI
- #SHOWMEWHATEXPERTSSAY
- #ERF2023

Aside from the previous videos and to make AI-PRISM's social media posts more engaging and captivating, **other multimedia materials, such as short video pills, banners and animations**, were created to accompany the most relevant posts, **adding up to 40 creativities produced**. More of these materials will be created as the project progresses.

Figure 15 AI-PRISM's short clip – SMEs need to know

Dissemination Plan

Dissemination is key for **AI-PRISM** as it aims not only at sharing results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers, but also at making these results available to the community contributing to the progress of science and technology in general. **AI-PRISM** has developed a flexible dissemination plan to build effective awareness of results among the key target audience identified, in order to facilitate the best use and uptake of the outcomes and research insights generated, reinforcing its impact. This dissemination is closely linked to the communication plan, and both to the overall project objectives, all to create impact beyond AI-PRISM's boundaries.

Similar to the communication plan, the dissemination plan is being implemented in three different phases. The key difference between the two, although closely interlinked, is that the 3 dissemination phases do not span throughout the whole project duration, but instead have a starting and an ending date. Of course, this does not mean that these phases cannot be extended or adjusted if necessary.

PHASE 1: Identify & Scrutiny (M1-M6)

During phase 1, **AI-PRISM** analysed the project's framework, with a special attention to obstacles that could slow down the dissemination activities, as well as to defining the priorities and actions for the first year of the project. During this phase, the reporting and follow-up tools and the Open Access Library were put into place, and the production of awareness publications started, beginning with the presentation of the project using the communication materials produced. Also, the preparatory actions to organise the first project workshops began.

PHASE 2: Outreach & Influence (M6-M18)

The main objective of this phase is to increase the awareness generated during the first phase and to mainly expose **AI-PRISM** achievements. All channels (including communication) have been adapted to the specific needs of the project to find the right means to engage and collaborate with the target groups. The participation in 9 workshops and 11 events during this phase (as detailed later in this document), as well as the scientific production of generated by the project partners, has helped boost the dissemination process.

PHASE 3: Embrace & Accept (M18-M36)

This phase, not yet started, will leverage the general awareness raised by the two initial phases, attracting more potential end users and clientele interested in **AI-PRISM** project's results. All outcomes of the two earlier phases will be evaluated and, if needed, priorities, measures and dissemination channels will be refined. Participation in events, workshops, and conferences as well as contributions to publications in targeted specific media online and printed trade and research journals will be implemented.

Dissemination Tools & Material

As already highlighted, communication and dissemination are closely interlinked therefore a number of tools are common for both. However, there are some dissemination tools specific to the dissemination and to creating impact for the project.

Project documentation

Documentation material in the form of **public deliverables** is made available through AI-PRISM's public repository and communicated through our communication channels. Such as:

- [D1.1 Technology benchmarking and Project Vision](#)

- [D1.2 Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis \(I\)](#)
- [D1.3 - Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis \(II\)](#)
- [D5.1-Task Analysis for Benchmarking and Design Requirements \(I\)](#)
- [D8.1 AI-PRISM Impact Master Plan.](#)

Scientific articles

AI-PRISM aims at publishing and contributing to peer-reviewed publications in top refereed scientific journals and conferences relevant to AI related topics and Manufacturing, to ensure that the technical achievements and experimental findings are known and exploited by a larger community.

The AI-PRISM production in terms of Scientific Publications is seeing an increment as the project progresses, proof of that is the **13 scientific pieces accepted, and another 5 submitted (and under consideration) to peer-reviewed Journals and Conferences.**

Peer-reviewed Scientific Publications in Journals:

- [PatchMixer: Rethinking network design to boost generalization for 3D point cloud understanding.](#) Published in the Image and Vision Computing journal. Partners involved: FBK.
- [Adaptive Beacon Period Configurator for Scalable LoRaWAN Downlink Applications.](#) Published in the IEEE Access (Volume 11). Partners involved: ITI, UPV.

Peer-reviewed Scientific Publications in Conferences:

- [Novel Class Discovery for 3D Point Cloud Semantic Segmentation.](#) Presented by FBK as a poster at the Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) 2023.
- [Revisiting Fully Convolutional Geometric Features for Object 6D Pose Estimation.](#) Presented by FBK as a workshop paper at the 2023 IEEE/CVF International Conference.
- [A Study to Compare YOLO Family Models for Metal Surface Anomaly Detection.](#) Presented by TECNOPAR at the 2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data.
- To collaborate or not to collaborate? How to determine the most suitable level of automation to increase workforce sustainability and production efficiency. Presented by CRA, NTTD and ANDREU at the ICRES 2023: 8th International Conference Series on Robot Ethics and Standards.
- Breaking the barriers: Multilingual user engagement to increase process engagement and technology acceptance in manufacturing. Presented by CRA at the AHFE 2023: 14th International Conference on Applied Human Factors and Ergonomics and the Affiliated Conference.

- On the development of programming by demonstration environment for Human-Robot Collaboration in a furniture painting cell. Presented by UPV at the 2024 European Robotics Forum.
- AI-based positioning on a micro scale. Presented by PIAP, Cranfield University and VIGO Photonics at the 2024 European Robotics Forum.
- Towards More Effective Human-Robot Collaboration via Accurate Pose Estimation. Presented by UPV and FBK at the 2024 European Robotics Forum.
- A Concise Taxonomy of Human-Robot Interactions and Soft Skills Synergy. Presented by TAU at the 2024 European Robotics Forum.
- AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions: Challenges in Human-Robot Collaboration Across Diverse Industrial Scenarios. Presented by UPV and PROFACTOR at the 2024 European Robotics Forum.
- Open-vocabulary object 6D pose estimation. To be presented by FBK at the IEEE / CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR) 2024.

Another **5 papers have been submitted and are currently under consideration:**

- 4 of them to the 12th International Conference on Interoperability for Enterprise Systems and Applications (2 by IKE and UPV, and 2 by UPV and CRAN).
- 1 to the European Conference on Computer Vision ECCV 2024 by FBK.

Figure 16 Presentation of poster at the Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) 2023

Open Access Library

Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, AI-PRISM provides open access to peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, brand assets and other resources generated within the project.

Regarding Open Access Library, AI-PRISM is using Zenodo OpenAIRE+ repository. A dedicated [Zenodo AI-PRISM community](#) and repository has been created, where scientific articles, publications, press releases and more can be found.

Thanks to the promotional strategy set up to make the project's results available to our stakeholders, we have achieved over +630 downloads and 2.200 views for the 12 documents uploaded to the CORTEX² Zenodo community, including:

- The Journal Article “PatchMixer: Rethinking network design to boost generalization for 3D point cloud understanding”.
- The 5 Public Deliverables produced up to this point and detailed in the previous section. Public deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo, pending potential update once validated by the European Commission.
- Communication and Dissemination materials, such as the official project logo, the launch press release (both in English and Korean, the 1st and 2nd newsletters, and other marketing materials).

Figure 17 Zenodo AI-PRISM community

Events

AI-PRISM has been very increasingly active regarding the participation in **events, with 13 participated until March 2024 and another already planned** for April 2024. It is worth mentioning the relevant role in the project in all the following:

[European Robotics Forum 2023](#) (ERF) 14th-16th March, 2023. Odense, Denmark

In its 2023 edition, the European Robotics Forum brought together the leading figures in robotics research and industry in Odense, Denmark. The AI-PRISM team actively participated in two workshops, was acknowledge in a third one, and set up a digital booth within the forum, with over 400 visitors.

[Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit](#) (DMIS) 25th-27th April 2023. Valencia, Spain

The AI-PRISM team organised the Robotics in Manufacturing workshop, while the Technological Institute of Informatics (ITI) also participated in another workshop.

[AI forum of Canada-Korea Conference on Science and Technology CKC 2023](#) 17th-21st, 2023.

Ottawa, Canada

Korean Partner Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute (ETRI) participated in the AI forum of CKC2023 and presented the human state assessment technology of the AI-PRISM project.

[Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition](#) (CVPR) – 18th-22nd June 2023. Vancouver, Canada

FBK participated in the IEEE CVPR 2023 conference in June, further spreading awareness of our project and its innovative contributions and presenting a paper.

[International Conference on Computer Vision](#) (ICCV) October 2 - 6, 2023. Paris, France.

FBK participated in the 8th International Workshop on Recovering 6D Object Pose (R6D), where it presented a paper.

[HaDEA/MCID Digital symposium](#). 8th March 2023. Bucharest, Romania

Andrei Rusu presented an overview of AI-PRISM at the HaDEA/MCID Digital Symposium in Bucharest, Romania. This presentation marked a significant milestone for our project and for NTTD RO as their first Horizon project.

[IQ Digital Summit](#). 14th June 2023. Cluj-Napoca, Romania

TDIH participated in this event, where it showcased AI-PRISM and its main objectives and developments.

A busy period in the participation of events was October 2023, where several AI-PRISM partners took part in the [Valencia Digital Summit 2023](#) as well as the [European Big Data Value Forum 2023](#), both held in Valencia, Spain, on the 26th – 27th and 25th – 27th of the month, respectively.

[AloD Community Forum and ICT-49 Final Event](#). 24 November 2023. Bologna, Italy.

Paul Chippendale from Bruno Kessler Foundation (FBK) represented the project at the AloD Community Forum and ICT-49 Final Event, where he pitched AI-PRISM at the “Enlarging AloD Community: New Initiatives” discussion.

[MEX Finland](#). 28 November 2023. Tampere, Finland

TAU, represented by Jose Martinez Lastra, was present at the fall meeting of MEX Finland, which is organized in cooperation with the University of Tampere, participating in a [panel discussion](#) on How the integration of Robotics and human-centricity work.

[Ultimate project Workshop on Trustworthy AI](#). 2nd February 2024. Online

In February 2024, Francisco Blanes (UPV), represented the project at the Ultimate project event (2nd February), through an online Workshop on Ethics, Hybrid AI, Safety &

Trustworthiness for robotics, and XAI, talking about the AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing.

Francisco Fraile

AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing

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Francisco Fraile is an associate professor and senior researcher in the fields of digital manufacturing and zero defects manufacturing, at the Polytechnic University of Valencia.

This presentation will provide an overview of the main innovations of AI-PRISM, a human-centred, AI-based solution ecosystem (with and without physical embodiment) targeting manufacturing scenarios. It will provide a high level overview of the main innovations, pilot use cases, and technology approach of this EU funded innovation initiative. This high-level presentation will serve as a catalyst to discuss with the audience synergies an potential collaborations with AI-PRISM.

Figure 18 Presentation of AI-PRISM at the Ultimate project Workshop on Trustworthy AI

[European Robotics Forum 2024](#). 13th - 15th March 2024. Rimini, Italy.

AIPRISM was a key project in the 2024 edition of the ERF, and very visible among the event attendees, which had 1.100 registrations. With activities such as

- Organisation of 2 workshops and participation in 1 invited talk.
- Presentation of 5 papers.
- COMAU booth with dissemination materials from the project
- It is worth mentioning that the Vigo Pilot in AI-PRISM received the **Sustainability Recognition** The certificate was awarded by the Topic group coordinators (Sharath Akkaladevi from PROFACTOR and Franziska Kirstein from Blue Ocean Robotics) at the official ERF 2024 award ceremony which was attended by 600 participants.

Figure 19 Sustainability Recognition award ceremony at ERF 2024

Upcoming events

[12th International Conference on Interoperability for Enterprise Systems and Applications. Enterprise Interoperability through Data, AI, and Robotics. I-ESA 2024.](#) 10th – 12th April 2024. Crete (Greece)

For this event, 4 papers have been submitted by the partner and are currently under consideration, and another workshop will be organised by the project.

Workshops

A total of **8 workshops have been organised, co-organised or participated** by the project partners and presenting AI-PRISM related developments, accumulating at this moment over **600 attendants**. Another workshop will be participated in April at I-ESA 2024 event.

European Robotics Forum 2023

- **Workshop** "Human-Robot Collaboration and AI for Smart Manufacturing" (Organizer).
- 10th **Workshop** on Hybrid Production Systems (Co-organiser).

Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit (DMIS)

- **Workshop** Robotics in Manufacturing (Organiser).
- **Workshop** Manufacturing Reconfiguration and Flexibility (Speaker).

Ultimate Project event

- Online **Workshop** on Ethics, Hybrid AI, Safety & Trustworthiness for robotics, and XAI (Speaker).

European Robotics Forum 2024 (13th - 15th March)

- **Workshop** "HRC and AI, Hype or Reality? From Pilots to Best Practices" and its related Insight session, where 4 AI-PRISM papers were presented (Organiser).
- 11th **Workshop** on Hybrid Production Systems and its related Insight session, where 1 AI-PRISM paper was presented (Co-organiser).
- **Workshop** on Harnessing Human-Centricity in Robotics Solutions for (E)DIHs and SMEs, where AI-PRISM was presented by TDIH (speaker).

Figure 20 Speakers of the AI-PRISM Workshop "HRC and AI, Hype or Reality" at the ERF 2024.

Upcoming workshops

Currently the project is in full preparation mode for its workshop at the **I-ESA 2024**.

Awareness publications

To showcase and make available to the public the different developments and updates of the project, different **Awareness Publications** have been produced, such as Press Releases, articles, newsletters, interviews, etc.

A total of **66 blog posts** have been produced, detailing different highlights of the project, such as:

- The participation in events, webinars and meetings

D8.2 AI-PRISM Dissemination and Communication Report (I)

- The scientific articles published by the partners
- Announcements and milestones
- Interviews to consortium members, etc.

Discover how **human-centered and AI-based solutions** are improving manufacturing processes, making workers' lives easier and healthier.

Figure 21 AI-PRISM website – News section with all blog posts and awareness publications

Communication & Dissemination Monitoring

Monitoring and adjusting both the Communication and the Dissemination Plan, on a frequent basis, is a fundamental element of the project's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed. It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met.

The main **Communication and Dissemination reporting and follow-up tools** are the following:

- **Excel shared on the project's online repository** for all partners to register their individual efforts and activities regarding events, peer-reviewed publications, etc.

CATEGORY	TITLE	DATE	DESCRIPTION	STATUS	PARTNER(S)
CONFERENCE	Ethics and Psychological Human Factors in Industrial Robotics	01/07/2023	The 24th International Conference on The Human Aspects of Advanced Manufacturing, Manufacturing Enterprises in a Digital World (http://www.ahfe.org/contact.html)	Accepted	CRA - FBK - UPV
CONFERENCE	2023 IROS IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots	1st-5th of October 2023	The 2023 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems is a large and impactful forum for the international robotics research community to explore the frontier of science and technology in intelligent robots and smart machines, emphasizing future directions and the latest approaches, designs, and outcomes.	Under Consideration	KEURLAN
CONFERENCE	IEEE CVPR 2023 "Novel Class Discovery for 3D Point Cloud Semantic Segmentation"	18-22 June 2023	The IEEE/CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR) is the premier annual computer vision event comprising the main conference and several co-located workshops and short courses. This year, CVPR will be a single track that everyone can attend everything. The focus will be on few selected plenary talks, scientific discussions at poster sessions and plenty of time for networking and socializing. Each year will be presented at a poster session. All	Accepted	FBK
JOURNAL	Adaptive Beacon Period Configurator for Scalable LoRaWAN Downlink Applications	4 August 2023		Published	ITL, UPV
JOURNAL	PatchMixer: Rethinking network design to boost generalization for 3D point cloud understanding	Volume 137, September 2023	The Image and Vision Computing journal has as a primary aim the provision of an effective medium of interchange for the results of high quality theoretical and applied research fundamental to all aspects of image interpretation and computer vision. The journal publishes work that proposes new image interpretation and computer vision methodology or addresses the application of such methods to real world scenes. It seeks to strengthen a deeper understanding in the discipline	Published	FBK
CONFERENCE	Revisiting Fully Convolutional Geometric Features for Object 6D Pose Estimation	3 October 2023	The 8th International Workshop on Reconstructing 6D Object Pose (R6D) workshop covers topics related to estimating the 6D object pose (3D translation and 3D rotation) from RGB/RGB-D images, which is an important problem for application fields such as robotic manipulation, augmented reality and autonomous driving.	Accepted	FBK
CONFERENCE	A Study to Compare YOLO Family Models for Metal Surface Anomaly Detection	15-18 December, 2023	The 2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (IEEE BigData 2023) will continue the success of the previous IEEE Big Data conferences. It will provide a leading forum for disseminating the latest results in Big Data Research, Development, and Applications.	Submitted	TEKNOPAR

Figure 22 Extract of AI-PRISM follow-up Excel (peer-reviewed publications)

- Content calendar for the communication team to plan and organise the contents generated and shared in all the channels of the project.

CONTENT CALENDAR								
MONTH/WEEK	DAY	RELEVANT DAY	OBJECTIVES	SOURCE	Twitter	LinkedIn	Video/Picture	Web Post
OCTOBER								
Week 2	Tuesday 4	Kick-off	To communicate about the kick-off meeting and introduce partners/objectives/project	Proposal	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15773015118	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:699306731432156624		
	Wednesday 5				https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15776131133	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:698136300444651620		
	Friday 7				https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15781106068	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:69840704317136120		
NOVEMBER								
Week 1	Wednesday 2	Press Release Zenodo	To communicate general information about the project	Proposal	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1587848185	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6993615115974843392	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Thursday 3	Press Release Zenodo			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1588093986	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:699382669113401020	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Friday 4	Press Release Vigo			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/158872931656	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6994295662832630927	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
Week 2	Monday 7	Press Release FBK			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15895991434	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6995165531769997824	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Tuesday 8	Press Release Zenodo	To have more downloads and views of our press release on Zenodo		https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15900174888	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6995775568072871936	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Thursday 10	World Science Day	To commemorate the day and linked it with the project objectives and purpose	https://www.un.org/en/observances/world-science-day/	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15906833703	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6996241686331862945	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
Week 3	Monday 14	SmartJourney Campaign 1.0	To give information about the keywords and concepts of the project	Proposal	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15914471586	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:699791012689387384	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Wednesday 16	SmartJourney Campaign 2.0			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15928079306	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:699791012689387384	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Friday 18	SmartJourney Campaign 3.0			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15933203347	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:699791012689387384	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
Week 4	Tuesday 22	SmartManufacturing Campaign 1.0	To explain why technology is important in the manufacturing sector	Proposal	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1592909723	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:70008580312931116	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Thursday 24	SmartManufacturing Campaign 2.0			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1593511448	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:700156661818290688	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Monday 28	EU SMEs Assembly Week Campaign 1.0			To raise awareness about the project launching a campaign about SMEs and digitalisation	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1597510017	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7003025481750953484	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link
	Wednesday 30	EU SMEs Assembly Week Campaign 1.0			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15979488588	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:70037109316697755492	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
DECEMBER								
Week 1	Friday 2	Press Release Teknopar	To communicate general information about the project	Proposal	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1598670013	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:70042446312048384	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Monday 5	The Evolution of Technologies event			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/1598784138	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7005559811172840168	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
	Wednesday 7	The Evolution of Technologies event			https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/15992764110	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:700608162373560608	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g
Week 3	Monday 12	European Year of Skills Consultation	To communicate general information about the project and its relation with a EU	https://7i.co/2XV3TcHT	https://twitter.com/AIPRISM/updates/16007264110	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:700608162373560608	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t4Vt4uCVj8d8mRtUkUwL72t4MPj/view?usp=share-link	https://zenodo.org/record/77744508/files/7/8a3-g

Figure 23 Extract of AI-PRISM content calendar

- Dissemination and Communication monthly meetings, to ensure an efficient organisation of all future activities in this area.

Final outcomes and results of the Dissemination and Communication plan will be reported in **D8.3 AI-PRISM Dissemination and Communication Report (II)** at Month 36.

International Cooperation

Objectives

According to the Grant Agreement, and as mentioned in D8.1, the objective of the international cooperation task is to identify relevant South Korean and Japanese initiatives and organisations with whom a potential collaboration and exploitation of synergies can be explored and performed.

The main strategy followed for the international cooperation was to identify the most relevant initiatives and partners in Japan and Korea that could benefit from AI-PRISM's outcomes.

Phases & timing - situation at M18

According also to D8.1, several phases for collaboration were established. Below we provide the current status for all of them.

PHASE 1: Mapping (M1- M12)

Identification of the most relevant initiatives and entities in South Korea and Japan by the consortium partners with local presence.

Korean partners from the consortium were contacted first so as to draft an initial list of cooperating partners. ETRI configured a list of seven potential entities working around collaborative robotics, and the list was shared with the Project Coordinator.

NTTD ES through its network in Japan made some efforts to reach Japanese entities, without much success during this initial phase.

Also, with the help of the Technical Coordinator, we defined the concrete form of collaboration with the entities from the list, which would be mainly in the form of joint workshops or publications and access to AI-PRISM Open Pilots.

This phase is currently closed.

PHASE 2: Contact (M13-M24)

Contact with the entity.

The Project Coordinator has contacted all these seven Korean entities previously reached by ETRI, getting a positive response from two of them, in particular:

- Hanyang University
- Korea Institute of Machinery & Materials (KIMM)

Therefore, a meeting with each entity was arranged (individually), counting also with the presence of the Technical Manager of AI-PRISM (UPV). These meetings served to present, on one hand, the AI-

PRISM project, and on the other, the research work around collaborative robotics carried out by Hanyang University and KIMM.

Also, in the meetings there were several discussions about how to find a collaboration and possible synergies. These synergies and interests were shared with the rest of the consortium in subsequent project meetings.

In the case of the Japanese partners, the coordinator has contacted two sister projects (COGNIMAN and Fluently) because to our knowledge, they have Japanese associated partners in their consortium. The proposal was to make a joint workshop between the project, mainly involving them. This proposal is currently under the evaluation of both coordinators.

PHASE 3: Cooperation (M25-M36)

Although the cooperation phase was supposed to start on M25, as a result of the above-mentioned meetings with Korean entities, TAU colleagues are currently drafting a paper to be shared with them to start a collaboration in that sense.

Conclusions

This report serves as the mid-project update on AI-PRISM's Dissemination and Communication strategy, offering insights into the **project's progress after 18 months of operation**. Over this period, AI-PRISM has achieved significant milestones, including the establishment of a unique visual identity, the development of primary digital communication channels, and the execution of collaborative initiatives in publication and promotion. These efforts have resulted in the creation of a cohesive brand identity for AI-PRISM, enhancing its online presence and fostering engagement within an expanding community.

The **Communication and Dissemination strategy** of AI-PRISM has evolved continuously to adapt to the project's dynamic nature, requiring ongoing collaboration from the consortium. This flexibility ensured that outreach materials, channels, and tools were refined to reflect the project's progress and notable achievements.

Over the last 6 months the **project has gained momentum both in its scientific production, as well as with increased presence in the ecosystem**.

As the project advances, the emphasis will shift towards more targeted dissemination activities, particularly in the technical and scientific domain. Consequently, efforts in fieldwork and networking will intensify in the later stages of the project, leveraging digital channels to maximise reach and visibility.

ANNEX A: Communication & Dissemination KPIs – Not Public

Table 1 Communication & Dissemination KPIs – Status M18

Measure	Indicator	Target	Status M18
Website	No. of Unique Visitors (monthly average)	200	65
Social media	No. of Followers (total)	5.000	1,450
	No. of Impressions (monthly average)	200	8,945
Publications	Peer-reviewed Scientific Publications in Journals	10	2
	Peer-reviewed Scientific Publications in Conferences	30	13
	Awareness Publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Articles • Newsletters • Press releases 	50	70
Events	No. of Events participated	50	13
Webinars/Workshops	No. of Webinars / Workshops (co-)organised	10	8
	No. of Registrations / Participants	300	600
Open Access	No. of Downloads (total)	1.000	+630